
The Effect Of Academic Resilience And Attitude On Managerial Performance

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the impact of academic resilience and attitude on management performance. Managerial performance is the outcome variable, whereas academic resilience and manager attitude are independent variables. Data was collected through a standardized survey questionnaire with items relevant to all dimensions and demographical characteristics of 120 managers of different enterprises from Peshawar. SPSS 24 is used for data analysis; Pearson's correlation and regression. The outcomes indicated that academic resilience and attitude positively and significantly affect managerial performance.

Keywords: Academic Resilience, Attitude, Managerial Performance,

1. INTRODUCTION

Individual attitudes are formed as a result of lifelong learning and growth. Academic learning uses precious resources to ensure that businesses working in complicated conditions and environments have responsible personnel (Bozer et al., 2014; Ullah, 2020). Information is critical to the success of businesses and the proper execution of responsibilities by managers. Managers and businesses are reaping the benefits of data analytics and big data technology. There are several categories of literature examining various sorts of organizations assessing individual resilience to their academic learnings and how this affects performance (Mählck, 2013). Academic learning resilience exposes a manager to domestic and international issues with governmental and non-governmental organizations that may serve as the backbone of executions (Van Hoek et al., 2019). Increased issues with business entities in becoming more cost efficient in prioritizing tasks to improve performance and task delivery can only be overcome with a positive attitude and a keep doing approach. Intellectual resilience is just as crucial as academic background (Wang & Zhang, 2021). Academic background is the foundation that allows a manager to comprehend current business trends and prepares them to be great performers.

The success of a manager is predicated on a combination of academic resilience and academic learning. Managers' ability to coordinate across organization partners is based on their ability to learn, which encourages participants to share more information and resources (Walker et al., 2011). A competent learned manager with resilience skills may improve an organization's performance and acceptance among its workers. Sustainability is always a challenge, with the economic, social, and environmental aspects of management performance having precedence when evaluating overall management performance, which managers may accomplish (Vig et al., 2011). A suitable decision support system is another factor to consider, since it might lead to system failure and poor performance. In every firm, the most important job is to keep track of each employee's performance at multiple levels while preserving the trust of rational resource allocation and data sharing while retaining transparency (Hernandez et al., 2021).

In today's developing world, the business sector can have a role model structure, with the manager's attitude serving as a guiding principle for successful execution and the process of comprehending and learning the mode of operations for progress. Capacity evaluation is important, but so is performance evaluation for being efficient during business executions, even if it can only be assessed after the fact. The firm learns about the manager's shortcomings and the possibility for building learning modules for the company's progress and success as a result of the post-assessment (Li & Yeung, 2019; Ullah, 2020). In order to make timely choices and execute tasks on time, the changing environment demands a shift from centralized authority to decentralized management (Academic Resilience, 2018).

Although managing an organization's network is not a new idea, current process advancements have resulted in further methodological adjustments that have led to network innovation at all levels. Integration, in which the entire system is integrated from start to finish to narrow the gap and improve the system's capabilities, has been one of the most essential and significant breakthroughs in the shift (Howell et al., 2018). The product is supplied correctly thanks to several levels of engagement. Providing excellent customer value and increasing customer happiness are important difficulties in maintaining long-term survival (De Feyter et al., 2020). An effective management system must have a very streamlined inventory management system, as well as the capacity to monitor the cost of operation and compatibility with all levels of involvement, to ensure a successful deployment (Das, 2019). A sustainable system is one that keeps moving forward in a positive way without failure or misalignment of the organization's goals among its members.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Academic resilience is one of the subcategories of resilience. It refers to the capacity to attain high levels of academic success despite the challenges faced throughout the struggle (Hwang & Shin, 2018). Students who are academically resilient develop regulated negative attitudes as well as adaptive attitudes in the face of hardship, according to a measure intended to evaluate academic resilience (Wyllie et al., 2020). It's also worth emphasizing that parental support is critical in ensuring students' academic resilience (Hwang & Shin, 2018). Previously, trauma was considered to be abnormal. In today's complicated lifestyle framework, many families and individuals are subjected to such terrible life situations (Wyllie et al., 2020). These traumatic events can happen once or numerous times, with long-term psychological, emotional, social, and physical implications for the individual who has been affected (Li & Yeung, 2019).

Academic resiliency is the capacity of a student or scholar to succeed in the face of hardship by adjusting current activities or establishing new ones, such as preparation, practice, or regulation (Academic Resilience, 2018). Individual resilience may be justified by comparing it to our body's inherent ability to deal with adversity, which is referred to as the immune system. Our immunity is boosted when we eat a well-balanced diet and live a healthy lifestyle (Wyllie et al., 2020). Scholars may also enhance their resilience and, as a result, their chances of success by focusing on improving their capacity to communicate ideas and perspectives (Van Hoek et al., 2019). It puts resilience into context and indicates a higher likelihood of success in the face of adversity.

Competent leaders who can contribute successfully to the attainment of organizational goals are required by organizations (Fang et al., 2017; Ullah,2020). As a result, all businesses must choose, develop, and support people who look to be capable of contributing. Despite numerous research on management styles, attitudes, and performance, the basic question of "what constitutes a successful manager?" remains unanswered (Piercy et al., 2012). Although research has revealed what leaders do and how they do it, the efficacy of these arrangements is unknown. One of the most noteworthy conclusions obtained from such studies is that situational variables are usually regarded crucial in determining effectiveness. Second, effective managers have a diverse set of skills at their disposal (Xue et al., 2020). Finally, excellent leaders consider situational considerations when deciding on the appropriate attitude in a specific situation. On the other hand, such assumptions do not give insight into the hidden processes that contribute to effective management (An & Argyle, 2020; Khan, Ullah, 2021). We're also curious about the new decision-making process that leads to a particular attitude (Carter et al., 2019). As a consequence, the primary goal here is to comprehend why leaders or managers behave in the manner that they do. An examination of this sort of management decision-making leads to a greater understanding of management attitude's efficacy, as well as advice for practitioners and researchers on how to choose and develop managers (Salehzadeh et al., 2015).

Supervisory qualities are necessary for a manager to be effective in leading others (Jung et al., 2021a). As a result, you should evaluate a manager's ability to impact these talents in ways that help the firm achieve its objectives (Jung et al., 2021b). It's also important to think about whether the management has set suitable goals, provided feedback, and applied rules fairly (Arnold et al., 2019). Every company's success depends on identifying intended outcomes and establishing the processes necessary to attain them (Sholihin et al., 2010). As a result, a manager's ability to organize, coordinate, and monitor employees' efforts to meet the company's objectives is important. A good manager should be able to translate an employee's expectations into action items, understand the company's business plan, and focus on effective communication and performance (Lei et al., 2019). The capacity of a manager to define priorities, apply appropriate pressure, and encourage his employees is crucial (Patiar & Wang, 2020).

On the topic of managers, there are a number of studies accessible. Leadership, operational management, and managerial training have all been identified as major sub-disciplines of the problem (Bebenroth & Froese, 2020; Khan, Ullah) (2021). The subdivisions are significantly supported by information of current organization attitude; nevertheless, it is crucial to highlight that each subdivision has evolved independently, and therefore no single cause can be held totally accountable for the managers' perspectives (Sheng et al., 2021). Although the impact of management and leadership on the functioning has been thoroughly studied, the two other sub-fields have received less attention, despite the fact that both seek to help generate staff effectiveness. As a result, all sub-divisions must be addressed gradually and completely in order to properly solve the challenges of leaders (Jung et al., 2021a). In fact, today's reality is that firms and organizations use a variety of sub-fields to create their models, yet there is a dearth of academic research on these issues. Some of the substantial disparities in management attitude among the sub-divisions are due to the mismatch between the notions of "leaders and managers" (Arnold et al., 2019).

3. RESEARCH PROBLEM

There is a lot of study on academic resilience, background, attitude, and performance variables, with each industry's significance presented differently (Roth et al., 2020). Each of these qualities has been studied individually in relation to organizational performance. Academic resilience, background, manager attitude, and performance all have a part in real-life circumstances, but the purpose of this study is to look at the link and effect of academic resilience, background, and manager attitude on performance in Pakistan's Peshawar region.

4. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- Is academic resilience beneficial to managers' performance?
- For a manager, how important are background elements?

- What effect does a manager's demeanor have on performance?

5. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Recognize the management advantages of academic resilience and determine how the manager's past impacts his or her attitude.

6. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

H1: Managerial academic resilience has a positive effect on performance. H2: The manager's performance is positively affected by background.

H3: Managerial attitude has a positive effect on performance.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

7. CONCEPTUAL FRAME WORK

8. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology is the scientific method for conducting a systematic inquiry. It is the approach of conducting research that is framed by the process and methodology (Jia & Gao, 2005). The researcher must pick one of the research approaches or mix both to achieve the desired result for the study subject. The research technique is a method for conducting research that is broken down into steps. Various research techniques have been disputed in several studies, however the two major forms of research may be classified as qualitative or quantitative (Lee & Cassell, 2013; Ullah,2020). The qualitative research technique is focused on gaining a full knowledge of a scenario or event via reflection, which is then included into the report analysis as a narrative. Quantitative research methods, on the other hand, rely on numerical data and statistics (Social Science Research: Principles, Methods, and Practices) (2 Ed., n.d.). The research design determines whether a study succeeds or fails (Long, 2014). The research design component is an organized framework of study in which the researcher uses the research technique to devise a suitable strategy for solving the problem and discovering a solution, which can then be documented and presented. Without a sample process, any research would be incomplete, and the use of statistical tools would be perplexing. Sampling design consists of mathematical functions that provide probability information for the selection of any item (Saragiotto et al., 2014).

An interview schedule is frequently used in qualitative research, with the data obtained being processed and analyzed in an explanatory manner. A survey questionnaire is used in quantitative research, and it comprises conceptual dimensions and variables. The data obtained is also analyzed, but primarily through statistical tests and processes employing statistical software. Because this is a quantitative study, a survey inquiry is conducted using a well-structured survey questionnaire (Aziz et al., 2018).

Manager Academic Resilience (Cassidy, 2016) with three sub dimensions (Perseverance, Reflecting and Adaptive Help-Seeking, and Negative Affect and Emotional Response), and Background (Billari et al., 2009) with three sub dimensions (Personal Factors, Social Factors, and

Reliability Statistics for Peshawar		
Dimensions	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Academic Resilience	30	.795
Background	24	.892
Manager Attitude	16	.834
Performance	27	.913
Overall Reliability	97	.945

Table 1 Reliability Statistics

Information Factors) (Individual Task Proficiency, Individual Task Adaptivity, Individual Task Proactivity, Team Member Proficiency, Team Member Adaptivity, Team Member Proactivity, Organization Member Proficiency, Organization Member Adaptivity, and Organization Member Proactivity). The data is merged before processing, but different types of data are kept separate and mixed as needed (Jamal & Goode, 2001; Khan, Ullah, 2021). This instrument has four dimensions to it. Academic resilience has 30 items, Background has 24 items, Manager Attitude

Variables	Parameters	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	40	33.3
	Female	80	66.7
Age	18 years -25 years	62	51.7
	26 years -35 years	38	31.7
	36 years – 45 years	17	14.2
	45 years and above	3	2.5
Education	Undergraduate	21	17.5
	Bachelor	32	26.7
	Master	65	54.2
	Ph.D.	1	.8
Monthly Income (PKR)	50001 – 100000	41	34.2
	100001 – 150000	29	24.2
	150001 - 200000	38	31.7
	200001 and more	4	3.3
Total		120	100

Table 2: Frequency and Percentage for demographical variables

has 16 items, and Manager Performance has 27 items, for a total of 97 items. In the study demography, a fourth demographical variable for the representation of the chosen sample has been added. The resulting instrument was assessed for dependability, which led to its acceptance because it is capable of evaluating this specific research subject with this specific population.

9. DATA ANALYSIS

The above table (Table 1) reveals that Cronbach's Alpha values for all four dimensions are much greater than 0.6, indicating that the above-mentioned dimensions are highly reliable. The maximum level of performance is in the dimension (0.913). With dependability scores of 0.892 and 0.834, the other two aspects of background and management attitude are likewise more reliable. Cronbach's Alpha value for the academic resilience component is 0.795.

The total number of respondents in this study was 120, with 66.7 percent of females and 33.3 percent of men. The frequency and percentages for various age groups are indicated above. It should be mentioned that among the 120 survey respondents, the biggest number (51.7%) belonged to the 18-25-year age group, while the lowest number (2.5%) belonged to the 45 year and older age group. The remaining population was divided into three age groups: 26-35 years old (31.7 percent), 36-45 years old (14.2 percent), and 36-45 years old (14.2 percent). The table above discusses the specifics of schooling. Only 0.8 percent of respondents held a PhD, whereas the majority of respondents (54.2%) had a Master's degree. The remaining respondents, 26.7 percent with a bachelor's degree and 17.5 percent with a bachelor's degree, were undergraduates. The income of 120 respondents on a monthly basis. The majority of respondents (34.2%) have a monthly income in the range of PKR50001-PKR100000, while 31.7 percent have a monthly income in the range of PKR150001-PKR200000. The table also shows that 24.2 percent of the population earns between PKR100001 and PKR150000 per month, with only 3.3 percent earning more than 200001.

Table 3: Academic Resilience One-Sample T-Test Analysis

Items	One-Sample T-Test		
	Test Value = 4		
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
I would not accept the tutor's feedback	-8.516	119	.000
I would use the tutor's feedback to improve my work	-.675	119	.501
I would just give up on study	-6.317	119	.000
I would use the situation to motivate myself for learning	.292	119	.771
I would change my career plans on study	-5.384	119	.000
I would see the situation as a challenge for study	-2.178	119	.031
I would do my best to stop thinking negative thoughts for study	-.976	119	.331
I would see the situation as temporary for study	-6.758	119	.000
I would work harder for study	-2.940	119	.004
I would try to think of new solutions for study	-.523	119	.602
I would blame the tutor for study	-6.053	119	.000
I would keep trying for study	-1.759	119	.081
I would not change my long-term goals and ambitions for study	-2.615	119	.010
I would look forward to showing that I can improve my grades	-.717	119	.475
I would use my past successes to help motivate myself	-2.520	119	.013
I would start to monitor and evaluate my achievements and effort	-1.788	119	.076
I would seek help from my tutors	-5.818	119	.000
I would give myself encouragement for study	-.758	119	.450
I would try different ways to study	.791	119	.431
I would set my own goals for achievement	1.679	119	.096
I would seek encouragement from my family and friends	-.387	119	.699
I would try to think more about my strengths and weaknesses to help me work better for study	-.223	119	.824
I would start to self-impose rewards and punishments depending on my performance on study	-7.534	119	.000
I would probably get annoyed with study	-9.585	119	.000
I would begin to think my chances of success at university were poor	-10.462	119	.000
I would probably get depressed for study	-5.342	119	.000
I would be very disappointed for study	-14.697	119	.000
I would begin to think my chances of getting the job	-4.686	119	.000
I would stop myself from panicking for study	-5.002	119	.000
I would feel like everything was ruined and was going wrong	-9.269	119	.000

Table 3 shows the results of the Academic Resilience One-Sample T-Test Analysis, which was carried out on 120 respondents using a survey questionnaire. There were 30 items in the Academic Resilience One-Sample T-Test. The analysis shows that the p value is less than 0.05, indicating that there are significant variations in respondent opinions, allowing all of these questions to be included in the research.

Items	One-Sample T-Test		
	Test Value = 4		
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
I am rebellious by nature	-5.272	119	.000
I am completely distinct and unique from everyone else	-1.946	119	.054
I am creative	-1.008	119	.315
I have a sense of being different from others	-1.541	119	.126
I complete my individuality	-1.248	119	.214
I am bold	-8.492	119	.000
I keep nonconformity	-13.412	119	.000
I have a sense of independence from others	-.180	119	.857
I share similarity with others in my group	-8.720	119	.000
I have my family nationality or nationalities	-2.641	119	.009
I have memberships in various groups	-5.773	119	.000
I am living the places where I have lived	-2.957	119	.004
I have a sense of belonging to my own racial group	-6.393	119	.000
I have a sense of belonging my gender group	-6.141	119	.000
I have a sense of belonging color of my skin group	-3.459	119	.001
I am being a citizen of my country	1.382	119	.170
I am aware of happenings in surrounding	-1.378	119	.171
I am active on internet	-1.817	119	.072
I am active socially	-2.065	119	.041
I am active on digital social sites	-5.545	119	.000
I keep updating myself with upcoming information	-2.189	119	.031
I see myself as a learner	.576	119	.566
I keep learning new information	.000	119	1.000
I keep seeking for new information	-1.118	119	.266

Table 4: Background One-Sample T-Test Analysis

Table 4 shows the results of the Background One-Sample T-Test Analysis, which was conducted on 120 respondents using a survey questionnaire. The One-Sample T-Test used 24 objects in the background. The analysis finds that the p value for the majority of the items is less than 0.05, indicating that there are significant variations in responder attitudes, allowing all of these questions to be included in the research.

Items	One-Sample T-Test		
	Test Value = 4		
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
I carry out the core parts of my job well	-4.482	119	.000
I complete my core tasks well using the standard procedures	-3.985	119	.000
I ensure my tasks are completed properly	.425	119	.672
I adopt well to change in core tasks	-4.571	119	.000
I cope with changes to the way I have to do my core tasks	-6.489	119	.000
I learn new skills to help me adopt to changes in my core tasks	-2.805	119	.006
I initiate better ways of doing my core tasks	-3.332	119	.001
I come up with ideas to improve the way in which my core tasks are done	-2.966	119	.004
I make changes to the way my core tasks are done	-3.664	119	.000
I coordinate my work with coworkers	-1.627	119	.106
I communicate effectively with my coworkers	-2.165	119	.032
I provide help to coworkers when asked, or needed	1.210	119	.229
I deal effectively with changes affecting my work unit	-3.398	119	.001
I learn new skills or taken on new roles to cope with changes in the way my unit works	-2.966	119	.004
I respond constructively to changes in the way my team works	-.682	119	.497
I suggest ways to make my work unit more effective	-.844	119	.400
I develop new and improved methods to help my work unit perform better	.657	119	.512
I improve the way my work unit does things	-3.449	119	.001
I present a positive image of the organization to other people	-.171	119	.865
I defend the organization if others criticize it	-3.821	119	.000

Table 5 Manager Attitude One-Sample T-Test Analysis

The Manager Attitude One-Sample T-Test Analysis was conducted on 120 respondents using a survey questionnaire, as shown in Table 5. The 16 items were used in the Manager Attitude One-Sample T-Test. The analysis finds that the p value for the majority of the questions is less than 0.05, indicating that there are significant variations in respondent attitudes, allowing all of these questions to be used in the research.

Table 6: Manager Performance One-Sample T-Test Analysis

Items	One-Sample T-Test		
	Test Value = 4		
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
I see my work schedule as a healthy activity to me	-2.976	119	.004
I believe routine work schedule is good to my performance	-4.330	119	.000
I feel pleasant on my daily routine	-4.392	119	.000
My daily routine following is fun for me	-3.657	119	.000
My work is enjoyable to me	-1.947	119	.054
I feel beneficial with my work schedule	-4.094	119	.000
People who are important to me believe I should follow my work	-.696	119	.488
People often ask me to do my routine activities with them	-5.821	119	.000
It is expected of me to do my routine activities	-1.500	119	.136
I feel under social pressure to do my routine activities	-8.533	119	.000
People who are similar to me do the same routine activities as me	-9.102	119	.000
I am confident I could do my activities if I wanted to	-2.940	119	.004
The decision to do my activities is beyond my control	-5.859	119	.000
Doing my activities is difficult to me	-12.726	119	.000
Whether I do my activities or not is entirely up to me	-5.363	119	.000
I choose when and where I do my activities	-3.369	119	.001

The Manager Performance One-Sample T-Test Analysis, which was conducted on 120 respondents using a survey questionnaire, is detailed in Table 6. There were 27 items in the Manager Performance One-Sample T-Test. The analysis finds that the p value for the majority of the items is less than 0.05, indicating that there are significant variations in responder attitudes, allowing all of these questions to be included in the research.

Table 7: Correlation and Regression Analysis

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Correlation (R)	Regression (B)	Sig.
Academic Resilience	Performance	.802	.857	.000
Background	Performance	.729	.853	.000
Behavior	Performance	.591	.541	

Table 7 contains the values for Correlation (R) and Regression (R). (B). Academic resilience correlates with performance (R-.802, B-.857), background correlates with performance (R-.729, B-.853), and attitude correlates with performance (R-.591, B-.541), all at a.000 significant level. As anticipated by the research, this is perfectly acceptable and good.

10. FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

The four components of data analysis employed to arrive at the research results are Academic Resilience, Background, Manager Attitude, and Performance. All four dimensions have Cronbach's Alpha values that are substantially higher than 0.6, suggesting that they are very dependable. Performance is the most essential factor (0.913). The other two elements of background and management attitude, with dependability scores of 0.892 and 0.834, are also more dependable. The academic resilience component has a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.795. The rest of the study results are supported by the One-Sample T-Test and Correlation and Regression Analysis. Academic resiliency, background, manager attitude, and manager performance are all things to think about. A one-sample T-test analysis was done on 120 respondents using a survey questionnaire that contained 30 items, 24 items, 16 items, and 27 items. The p value is less than 0.05 in this analysis, showing that there are significant differences in respondent opinions, meaning that all of the items were authorized for the study. According to the Correlation and Regression Analysis, the basic correlation's strength is sufficient and good. Independent variables that influence Manager Attitude include academic resilience, background, and performance. The Coefficients tab shows the details for each predictor variable, as well as how the constant and Manager Attitude influenced the results. The coefficients provide details on the predictor factors while also indicating that the constant, as well as Manager Attitude, Background, and Academic Resilience, played a significant effect.

The ultimate conclusion of the study is based on data that indicate that the research problem was solved by answering research questions and meeting goals. The initial aim is to learn about the advantages of academic resilience for managers, which have been demonstrated and accepted by a high correlation and regression value, demonstrating that academic resilience makes a manager strong for learning and growth. The second objective is to investigate the factors that influence a manager's attitude, which has shown to be highly relevant when using statistical T-test to shape attitude. The third objective is to look at the function of a manager's attitude in performance, as evidenced by correlation and regression analysis, which shows that a manager's attitude has a significant impact on performance. Academic resilience provides a substantial contribution to manager performance, according to the first study question, with a strong correlation and regression value. Background components are highly essential for a manager who has a high T-test acceptance and is further approved with a high correlation and regression value, thus the second question was answered. The high degree of acceptance in T-test, correlation, and regression analysis may explain why the third question indicated that a manager's attitude had an influence on performance. Statistical tests reveal a significant

relationship and effect of management attitude on performance, as well as a significant contribution of academic resilience and background on performance.

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